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Synthesis and Amoebicidal Activity of Some New N-(2-Nitro 4, 5-Dimethoxy Benzoyl) Glycine Hydrazones.

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A number of *o*-dimethoxy substituted derivatives¹⁻⁵ are reported to possess high amoebicidal activity comparable to that of emetine against *E. histolytica*. It is believed that emetine undergoes some degradation in the system and the *o*-dimethoxy nucleus is the essential part of the degradation products⁶⁻⁸. Recently a large number of hydrazones⁹⁻¹¹ have shown significant amoebicidal activity. Moreover, the amoebicidal activity of compounds containing -CONH- group in halo acetamides¹²⁻¹⁴, has long been known. These observations led us to synthesise some new N-(2-nitro 4, 5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine hydrazones and evaluate their amoebicidal activity.

Experimental

The title compounds were synthesised according to the route outlined below.

Ethyl ester of glycine¹⁵ and N-(2-nitro-4,5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine ester¹⁶ were prepared according to reported methods. Melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. Compounds were routinely checked for their homogeneity by tlc on silica gel G.

(a) *N*-(2-nitro-4,5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine hydrazide: A mixture of N-(2-nitro-4, 5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine ethyl ester (0.01 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mole) was refluxed in absolute ethanol (100 ml) for 8 hrs. The excess solvent was distilled off, the residue cooled, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. m.p. 180° (N% for C₁₁H₁₄N₄O₆: Found 18.38, Calcd. 18.79).

(b) *N*-(2-nitro-4,5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine hydrazones: N-(2-nitro-4,5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine hydrazide (0.001 mole) was condensed with an appropriate substituted aldehyde or ketone (0.001 mole) by refluxing a mixture of their ethanolic solution for 4 hrs. The desired hydrazones obtained on concentration and cooling were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

The pertinent data of the compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

Amoebicidal activity: All the compounds (Table 1) were tested for their amoebicidal activity by the following methods.

The test compound was dissolved in dimethyl formamide. The solution was diluted with water and sterilised by autoclaving at 15 lb per sq. inch pressure for 15 minutes. Thermolabile compounds were tested as such but Penicillin in 1000 and Streptomycin in 1000 µg/ml were added to the media. Tests were conducted at pH between 6.7 to 7.0.

Axenic *E. histolytica* (strain 200: NIH) was maintained in modified IPS-1 medium containing 0.2% cystine in screw capped tubes (16×122 mm). 10,000 amoebae/ml of the medium as determined by Haemo-

**Part of this work will be included in the Ph.D. thesis of Rashmi Srivastava.

TABLE 1—N-(2'-NITRO-4,5-DIMETHOXY BENZOYL) GLYCINE HYDRAZONES*

Sl. No.	R	R'	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen %	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	H	C ₆ H ₅	158	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₅	14.32	14.50
2.	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	170	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₇	13.06	13.46
3.	H	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	247	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₆ Cl	13.11	13.31
4.	H	<i>o,p</i> -Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	220	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ Cl ₂	12.15	12.30
5.	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	238	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₈	16.12	16.24
6*	H	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ , <i>m,p</i> -(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	173	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₁₀	14.05	14.25
7.	H	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ , <i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	137	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₈	12.54	12.96
8.	H	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	221	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₇	13.61	13.93
9.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	135	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆	14.32	14.00
10*	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	177	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆	14.15	14.00
11.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	121	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆	13.22	13.52
12.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	142	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₆ Cl	12.53	12.88
13*	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	186	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₇	13.35	13.02
14.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	181	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆	12.32	12.12

*Yields ranged between 45-60%.

*Satisfactory analysis for C and H.

Showed ir spectral bands at 1700-1650 cm⁻¹ (C=O amide); 3350-3100 cm⁻¹ (Sec. N-H); 1650-1510 cm⁻¹ (C=N-).

cytometer count were inoculated at the bottom of the tubes and the tubes were incubated at 37° in an upright position. Vigorously growing cultures of amoebae from 72 hrs old tubes were used for inoculating the media containing the test compounds. The method of testing the action of drugs on trophozoites of *E. histolytica* is as follows :

One ml of the test solution was added to 8 ml of modified TPS-1 medium containing 0.2% cystine in screw capped tubes and then mixed by inverting the tubes. The tubes were left in an upright position overnight in order to absorb the dissolved atmospheric oxygen. 1.0 ml of the inoculum, containing 10,000 amoebae was then added to the bottom of the tubes. The tubes were incubated in an upright position at 37° without inverting them. The amoebicidal end point was determined microscopically during 72 hrs under an inverted microscope. In doubtful cases subcultures were made. In each set of experiments, tubes in duplicate at each dilution of a compound and two controls were included. The standard drugs used were emetine hydrochloride and metronidazole.

Result

Of the fourteen compounds synthesised, only three compounds no. 6, 8 and 12 (Table 1) showed an amoebicidal activity at 125 µg/ml as compared to 62.5 µg/ml and 7.8 µg/ml of emetine hydrochloride and metronidazole respectively.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some New Mannich Bases Derived from 7-Hydroxy-4-Phenyl Coumarin

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COUMARINS are known to possess antifungal and antibacterial properties^{1,2}. 7-Hydroxy-4-phenyl coumarin, a naturally occurring coumarin, was found

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